

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D1.3 Data Management Plan

Call and Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is dedicated to the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the INTEGER project, the goal is to describe how data will be handled during the INTEGER project and along the required 5 years period, after the project ends.

The DMP is guided by different factors:

- i) Legal framework,
- ii) Open data policy (FAIR approach),
- iii) Project needs (what sort of data will be necessary and used during the project).

Based on these three aspects we have defined a strategy and procedures to handle data in the project, taking in special account the GDPR and each partner's national laws that are to be known and applied correctly.

This document has 4 main parts.

- 1) Section 1 and 2 introduce what is data management, open access and the FAIR concept. These are the rules and approach taken by the project as part of a Horizon Europe CSA¹.
- 2) Section 3 present what data will be used, its purpose and how it will be identified. This includes the metadata, which is the file describing the dataset, that will be used.
- 3) The third part, section 4, presents the procedures that will be followed to manage data. In this section it is described the overall structure and procedures defined for the data management.
- 4) Finally, section 5 gives an overview (brief description) of the datasets foreseen to be used in INTEGER.

The document is complemented with the conclusions and the annexes, where an example of the informed consent and the datasets can be found.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
HE	Horizon Europe
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
WP	Work-Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
FAIR	FAIR principle for open data: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
DPC	Data Protection Coordinator
DPO	Data Protection Officer

1 Data management framework

1.1 Introduction

The INTEGER DMP will describe in detail the data that the project will collect or generate, the data that will be shared or made open and how data is described. It will also identify data protection laws and regulations at EU² and national³ level to be followed and the methodologies to protect data. As a European project, INTEGER will define recommendations to be followed to make research data compliant with the FAIR approach. Finally, the DMP will also propose a management structure, procedures, and what tools and resources can be used to curate and preserve data during and after the project lifetime.

1.2 General overview

The three points to consider when dealing with data in INTEGER are: The Open Access of publications, Open Data, and the IPR restrictions included in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. As a general rule, partners must take into account that unless it goes against the legitimate interest of the beneficiaries, the results must be open and disseminated to the society and scientific community. This means that the beneficiaries have the right to protect the results in case the institution plans to protect or exploit the results. In the following sub-sections, it is provided more detail on how it is recommended (by the European Commission) to open access and data within a Horizon Europe project.

1.2.1 Open Access in Horizon Europe

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing, free of charge to any user, online access to all peer-reviewed scientific information and all the research data. In consequence as indicated in article 17 of the Grant Agreement the members of the consortium must:

- *at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications,*
- *immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and,*
- *information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.*

²https://commission.europa.eu/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/know-your-rights/freedoms/protection-personal-data_en

³ https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en

To ensure open access, it has been agreed to use OpenAIRE⁴ to link different Zenodo⁵ repositories. OpenAIRE and Zenodo are both free-to-use resources developed with the objective of supporting the EU scientific and research community to comply with regulations, offer safe sharing services of datasets and publications, gain visibility, and facilitate reporting with EC's public grants programmes (i.e Horizon Europe).

1.2.2 Open Data in Horizon Europe

Also as stated in the GA (article 17) each beneficiary must ensure open access⁶ to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- *As soon as possible and within the deadlines, set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated and compliant with the European Open Science Cloud⁷ (EOSC),*
- *As soon as possible and within the deadlines, set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’, unless providing open access would in particular: be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests, or the beneficiary’s obligations under the Grant and Consortium Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified and registered in the Datasets spreadsheet (further details in section 3.1),*
- *Provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data,*
- *Metadata⁸ of deposited data must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.*

It is important to include in the metadata all the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”,
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number,

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/> OpenAIRE is a Non-Profit Partnership, established in 2018 as a legal entity, OpenAIRE A.M.K.E, to ensure a permanent open scholarly communication infrastructure to support European research.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/> Zenodo is an open repository developed by the OpenAIRE program and managed by CERN.

⁶ Free of charge online access for any user

⁷ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁸ Metadata refers to the information describing the dataset (i.e. author(s), publication date, size, etc.). Most of the open platforms for open access offers repositories using standard metadata systems.

- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable and a persistent identifier⁹.

Figure 1 Example of Zenodo's metadata (image by Faircookbook¹⁰)

1.2.3 IPR commitments in INTEGER

Apart from the commitments regarding the Open Access and the Open Data, the other main commitments linked with the IPR included in the GA and the CA are detailed in article 8 of the CA which states that:

- Results are owned by the Party that generates them. In case of joint ownership, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to exploit the joint results as it sees fit and to grant non-exclusive licenses, without obtaining any consent from, paying compensation to, or otherwise accounting to any other joint owner, unless otherwise agreed between the joint owners.*

The regulation of access to background is defined in the article 9 of the CA.

1.3 GDPR compliance

INTEGER will deal with personal data, in some cases sensitive data. Therefore, the consortium will set up all necessary measures to protect its users while participating in the project. For instance, any user involved in any project activity will be informed when data is gathered, knowing what sort of data will be gathered, how it will be used and what are his/her rights as participant in the project. The project will follow the legal obligations of the data protection

⁹ A persistent identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital resource. <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971013-What-are-persistent-identifiers-PIDs->

¹⁰ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/findability/zenodo-deposition.html>

legislation according to the European (The Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016¹¹) and local laws of each corresponding partner.

The INTEGER strategy is to minimize the use of personal data as best as possible, limiting it to the needed information to fulfil the action and resource as much as possible to mechanisms that

EACH PARTNER, IS SOLE RESPONSIBLE OF THE PROPER APPLICATION OF NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN REGULATIONS AND LAWS IN TERMS OF DATA PROTECTION AND PRIVACY. EACH PARTNER IS RESPONSIBLE FOR ITS ASSOCIATED PARTNERS AND THIRD PARTIES INVOLVED IN THE INTEGER 4H PROJECT TO FOLLOW THESE REGULATIONS.

intent to protect participants (anonymized, aggregated data, etc.). Following this strategy will ensure that the risk of harming individual rights is kept as low as possible and allows easy use of the collected data for academic research purposes. In relation to the collected data, INTEGER will ensure honesty and transparency towards research subjects and, notably, getting free and informed consent from Third parties. There will be no dissemination of personal information without prior written consent from Third parties involved in INTEGER actions.

All users participating in project activities will be informed about the activity, and how data will be used, and requested to provide their written consent that confirms that they read and understood the provided information and that they gave their consent on an informed basis, before the activity starts.

- **INTEGER 4H Platform:** Any user joining the project community through the INTEGER 4H platform will read and provide their consent according to data usage and management.

Figure 2 Privacy statement used in the INTEGER-4H platform

¹¹Council of the European Union, European Parliament. (2016, April 27). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance). Publications Office of the EU. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3e485e15-11bd-11e6-ba9a-01aa75ed71a>

- **INTEGER activities:** In case the project approaches users in on-site activities, or users that have not provided their consent through the platform, there will be an alternative process. In this case, an informed consent (available in English) has been prepared (see annex I). This informed consent has two parts. A first one where the activity and purpose of data collection and use is explained, and a second one, where users agree with the terms explained in the first part, together with how data and image rights will be handled.

No users will be participating in any project activity without having read, understood, and provided their consent.

1.4 Data sharing

One of the main features of INTEGER is that three different sites, three *col-laboratories*¹² spread across Europe, will work together and each of them will collect different sets of data. To achieve this goal, it is essential to have a tool that allows data to be shared between partners quickly and securely (see 3.3.2 for further information).

It is mandatory that all data are kept and shared securely, ensuring that users' rights are protected throughout the whole process (and project). Each partner will be responsible for implementing appropriate mechanisms for handling the data that is shared. All data that is or will be shared between INTEGER partners containing sensitive data will be properly anonymised.

Throughout the life of the project, various datasets will be generated, some of which will contain personal or sensitive data of external users involved in the project activities. For the purposes of the project, or following the principle of open science, it will be necessary to share this data (e.g., as part of research publications) ensuring no data leaks or security violations take place.

1.5 Data security

To protect the data generated, used, or processed during the INTEGER project it is important to understand the potential threats, align the layers of defence and understand the activities related to the management and protection of data during the life of the project and take measures as necessary.

INTEGER will follow the five pillars of information security¹³ to ensure proper security in its data management: confidentiality; integrity; availability; authenticity; and non-repudiation.

1. Confidentiality: to consider protecting data is to ensure data confidentiality. To do so, it is essential to encrypt the data and restrict access so that only authorized persons can access the data.

¹² It is a neologism to express the next generation of quadruple or n-helix living labs. (<https://integercollab.eu/what-is-integer/>)

¹³ *The 5 pillars of information security and how to manage them.* (2022, July 18). Inifinit-O Resource Center. <https://resourcecenter.inifinit-o.com/blog/the-5-pillars-of-information-security-and-how-to-manage-them/>

2. Integrity: to guarantee the integrity of the data, it is essential to prevent third parties from manipulating INTEGER's information system, thus avoiding the alteration, modification, or destruction of the information.
3. Availability: For the information system to function, it is important that authorized persons can access and have access to the data. For this it is important that the information services used in INTEGER are robust and functional, avoiding crashes or malfunctions.
4. Authenticity: it is important that users confirm their identity through an authenticity system, such as a double authenticity system, to secure the transmission of information and access to INTEGER's systems and resources.
5. Non-repudiation: When sharing information, it is important that both, the sender and the receiver, have confirmation not only of receipt but also that the identities of each are authorized, and that is the system that makes impossible to deny sending, receiving, or accessing the data, as there is a record of this.

Each partner (and possible linked Third-parties) is responsible to ensure that all these principles are met during the project. In addition to the above-mentioned considerations, the consortium partners who have their own data security policies will be followed and considered in the development of INTEGER's data protection activities.

I2CAT, as Project Coordinator, will act as the data protection coordinator (DPC) of the project, assisted by the single point of contact for data privacy of each of the consortium members (data protection officers, DPO), to manage such data. This responsibility does not prevent the partners from having their own data protection roles, always following their own data protection rules, regional regulations and GDPR.

1.6 Archiving and preservation

While INTEGER is active and following the security guidelines in the previous section (see 1.4), raw data produced by the project will be stored by the partners themselves according to their need or convenience. Once the project is finished, the consortium will have chosen a secure repository where the general data of INTEGER project will be stored and preserved.

The project foresees the use of Zenodo as the platform for storing and managing the data generated and Open Aire for linking the databases and publications. In addition, the project will disseminate the open results through its website (<https://integercollab.eu/>), its platform INTEGER-4H (<https://theglocal.network/>), and the social media..

Following as stated in the Grant Agreement (page 11, section 6 Other) the consortium commits to keep records of all documentation 5 years after the project period expires.

2 FAIR Data approach

Following the line of the European Commission in its data strategy¹⁴ pursuing knowledge cloud-based fostered by open access data, the INTEGER project is committed to follow the guidelines of the Horizon Europe programme and make all its data as open as possible following the FAIR principles.

In this respect, this document will portray how the project's publications, be they documents, software or datasets, will be managed and treated following the FAIR principles.

The guidelines set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement as well as local and European legislation will be followed regarding the treatment of personal data, ensuring their correct anonymisation.

2.1 Introduction: What is FAIR?

Projects such as INTEGER might generate data that requires proper management, storage and processing for its use. As the scientific community is already committed to Open Science, a set of best practices for handling and publishing scientific data is required.

The publication in 2016 of the article *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship* in the journal *Nature* [4] data brought about a change in the way open access data was treated and published, creating a guide to ensure that digital publications are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and ensures the Reuse of resources.

2.2 INTEGER measures to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable.

Having explained in the previous section what FAIR data are, we proceed to explain how the INTEGER project will follow and apply these processes and how the guidelines set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement will be followed, in addition to respecting both local and European legislation regarding the processing of personal data and ensuring their correct anonymisation.

2.2.1 Findable

In order for data to be findable, i.e. easily findable datasets by the community in online platforms through search tools, the consortium commits to always assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI¹⁵) to the data. In addition, all datasets will have to be properly described according to a metadata schema, such as Dublin Core¹⁶.

INTEGER will deposit all its publications that can be shared without restriction in a centralised repository accessible on the web. The most prominent option at present is the OpenAIRE-run open data portal, Zenodo. This portal allows researchers to publish in various formats and

¹⁴ *European data strategy*. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en#projected-figures-2025

¹⁵ <https://www.doi.org/>

¹⁶ DCMI. *DublinCore*. <https://www.dublincore.org/>

typologies such as articles, presentations, or datasets. It also assigns a DOI to every publication, making it easy for researchers to register.

2.2.2 Accessible

In line with the open data policy, INTEGER is committed to ensuring access to all datasets it generates, collects or produces during the lifetime of the project.

Although due to the sensitivity of some of the data that may be generated through the collection of data in the project activities, these will not be published until they are properly processed or will have certain access restrictions to ensure GDPR is followed. Although not all the data contained in the datasets will be fully open access, the metadata describing them will be.

2.2.3 Interoperable

At this stage of the project, although the actual nature of the data is still unknown, and it is not yet possible to list a set of guidelines to be followed to guarantee the interoperability of the data. The use of open software and the use of controlled vocabularies, as well as the avoidance of ontologies that are not in common use are examples of the project approach towards interoperability.

2.2.4 Re-usable

INTEGER is committed to license datasets to third parties under the most appropriate licence, considering the intellectual property rights of the project partners as defined in the consortium agreement.

Implementing European Commission policy, Open Research Europe strongly recommends using a certified or trusted community-recognised repository as the first choice for depositing data. When no community-approved repository exists, a trusted general data repository (such as Zenodo), an institutional repository or a national repository will be chosen.

3 Data Management

The DMP defines how the data that the project will generate will be stored, localized, preserved and in which cases will be publicly disclosed. This DMP follows the guidelines of the Digital Curation Centre (www.dcc.ac.uk) on how to implement DMP and the recommendations of the EC as published in the Guidelines on FAIR.

3.1 Purpose of the Data Collection & Relation to the Objectives of the Project.

The data generated in the project will be created through workshops and publications and is related with the project objectives in the following way:

- **WP1-COORDINATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING:** Datasets generated in WP1 might be limited to contact lists (e.g. mailing lists), so we can consider that no open datasets will be generated within this WP.
- **WP2- LEARNING FOR 4H COLLABORATORY CO-CREATION; WP3-REGIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS' AS COLLABORATORY TESTBEDS; WP4-INTEGER 4H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COLLABORATORY DEPLOYMENT:** At the core of the project, we have WP2, WP3 and WP4 where most of the datasets are expected to be generated given the interrelated nature of the work among the three central work packages of the project. Here we can find a large variety of formats, spanning from lists of participants in project events, minutes, pictures, questionnaires, data gathered in events, recordings of sessions, presentations, posters and public documentation (e.g. INTEGER's core model).
- **WP5-ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION:** This WP might overlap with the previous block of WPs, since some content might be produced across tasks. In particular, here we can expect to generate and share as open datasets media content (e.g. video testimonials, interviews, presentations, posters, leaflets, etc.). Publications like papers or research articles are also potential outcomes.

3.2 Data identification

During the lifetime of INTEGER project several datasets from various consortium members, representing different domains, will be produced. For every open dataset, the consortium will provide a valid license or proof of ownership. INTEGER will remain compliant with GDPR¹⁷, and the ePrivacy and NIS directives¹⁸ in its design. The consortium, however, recognises that there might arise a need to openly publish other data generated by the project. In such a case, the consortium will prioritise the use of standardised and interoperable data and file formats when possible. In cases of unstructured, non-standardised data, the consortium will implement a data format to be published as an INTEGER specification.

Data sets will be described by: *Name of the dataset, Reference, Ownership, Level of public access, Description, Data types, Data formats & size, Archiving, Curation & Preservation mechanism,*

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32002L0058>

¹⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

Data source, Is the data reused or owned? If they contain data that is sensitive (under data protection law, such as personal data), and Use for the project.

The data, however, will not be made publicly available if there are issues with Security, Confidentiality, Privacy and/or Data Protection.

The datasets to be generated are listed below in Table 1. It is possible, as the project evolves, this table is modified with additions or removals of datasets. The potentially updated table will be presented in the next versions of the DMP.

Field	Description
Name of the dataset	Name of the dataset.
Reference	<i>WPx_Tx_title_year_month_verx_PARTNER_dataset.ext</i>
Ownership	Institution's contact person for data management.
Level of public access	Access Level should be one of the following: Open the data is made publicly available to third parties, with or without restrictions); Restricted (the data is only available to members of the consortium, and the EU Commission for revision and evaluation purposes if needed).
Description	Brief description of the datasets that have been identified by the consortium partners as relevant to the different trials.
Data types	The standard you use to describe the data (CIM; Open ADR; ISO/IEC 20547-4:2020; NIST SP 1500-4r2; etc.)
Data formats & size	Data format (.pdf, .doc, .xls, etc.) Tools or specific software (if needed) and size of the files included in the dataset.
Archiving	Where data is stored.
Curation & preservation mechanism	DOI and preservation mechanisms of the dataset.
Data source	Where, how or when the data originates. It can also be due to a project, industry, person, study, etc.
Re-used/Owned	If you were to use a dataset already published in the project. Citing it correctly specifying access, location and ownership of use.
Sensitive data	Yes or No. In case of YES, it must be notified to the Data Manager and check what measures apply.

Table 1 Datasets description example

Possible changes taking place during the execution of INTEGER affecting the information described in this deliverable need to be registered. Periodic checks and updates will be performed to ensure information is up to date. This update will be done online (via email), where the Data Manager at i2CAT will remind partners to check existing datasets or update with new ones. An updated (and consolidated) list of datasets will be documented in a spreadsheet stored in the INTEGER repository (hosted by i2CAT). Only project partners will be able to access at any time for consulting purposes or to update the information available.

4 Internal procedures and resources

4.1 Roles and consortium coordination

To monitor and manage the project data, it is important to define and set up a governing body. A structure that allows coordinating all partners to provide support when necessary and identify potential risks or mistakes in how data is handled.

This is the organisation structure proposed for INTEGER (see Figure 3).

Data Protection Coordinator, DPC (i2CAT): Within the coordinating entity, a person is appointed as DPC, which main purpose is to track potential datasets in the project and make sure they are updated in the data control datasheet, provides advice to partners based on the feedback provided by the PMO (project management office at i2CAT), supports the use of storing tools, coordinates the preparation of the data management plan, and provides status reports under request.

Project management office, PMO (i2CAT): In charge of all legal and administrative questions related to INTEGER, they will also support partners (through the DPC) on GDPR and data management questions.

Data protection officer, DPO (all partners): To have clear roles defined, each partner will identify a person in charge of data management and protection within their organisation. This person will interact with the DPC.

Figure 3 Organisational structure for data management in INTEGER

It is expected that the DPC will approach all DPOs at least twice per year in order to update the datasets, and make sure that they are accessible to the project audience. Any DPO can approach the DPC for consultation at any time. The contact person will be introduced to the project partners and its contact details will be available in the project platform and the dataset identification file.

Name	Email	Entity
Antonia Caro (DPC)		i2CAT
EPO department		i2CAT
Rebeca Martín		FURV
Javier Ganzarain		AFE
Luis Dias		SHINE
Stuart Anderson		F6S
Kai Fritze		HAM
Monika Tokarczyk		UJ
Aleksandra Szydłowska		KTP

Table 2 List of DPOs per entity (July'23)

4.2 Data storage, sharing and protection tools

INTEGER will use two tools to share data, knowledge and documents between project partners: Google Drive¹⁹ and the Integer's platform – Integer 4H²⁰.

- Google Drive:** It is the main tool for storing, sharing and editing documentation provided by i2CAT as project coordinator. All project partners will gain access to the project folders. Google drive is a well-known solution for handling files, as well as for online editing. Google drive was also chosen since it is compatible with the INTEGER platform.
- INTEGER 4H:** INTEGER 4H is the platform customised for the project purposes. One of its functionalities is to facilitate storage and sharing of information and documentation, including publications, presentations, and other datasets. It is used to store final documentation and to complement other (external) tools.

Besides these resources provided by the project, there are other tools and resources that will be used throughout the project, namely google forms, that is used to collect information internally and externally.

Each partner will be responsible for implementing the appropriate mechanisms for dealing with the data to be shared. All data that must be shared between INTEGER partners containing sensitive data will be properly anonymised. For this purpose, the use of the Amnesia tool²¹, which is managed by OpenAIRE, is recommended.

¹⁹ <https://www.google.com/drive/>

²⁰ <https://integer4h.theglobal.network/company/smart-integer>

²¹ Terrovitis, M., Tsitsigkos, D., & Dimakopoulos, N. (n.d.). *Amnesia Anonymization tool*. Amnesia Anonymization Tool - Data anonymization made easy. <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/index.html>

OpenAIRE offers other tools like Argos²² for data processing and Zenodo²³ for data publishing, tools that are encouraged to be used within INTEGER.

I2CAT will provide support and advice in the processes of identification and data processing in its role as DPC. It will be at the disposal of the partners and will send emails for reminders and to follow up on the correct identification of the possible datasets generated by INTEGER.

4.2.1 Zenodo community

At this date, there is already a community, within ZENODO, created by the coordinator where documentation can be uploaded. This community will host all project documentation and publications.

Table 3 INTEGER's links to Zenodo (some links are hidden for security reasons)

Collection URL:
https://zenodo.org/communities/integer4h_101096563/
Above address links directly to INTEGER community collection.
Upload URL:
https://zenodo.org/deposit/ [REDACTED]
Above address will automatically ensure people who use it will have their record added to INTEGER community collection.
Curation URL:
[REDACTED]
Above address links to INTEGER's private curation URL. You will find all uploads pending INTEGER curation.
Harvesting URL:
https://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-integer4h_101096563&metadataPrefix=oai_dc
Above address links to an OAI-PMH feed, which can be used by other digital repositories to harvest this community.

Figure 4 INTEGER's Zenodo community (20/07/2023)

²² OpenAIRE. Argos. <https://argos.openaire.eu/user-guide>

²³ OpenAIRE - CERN. Zenodo. Research. Shared. <https://zenodo.org/>

5 DATASETS

5.1 I2CAT

- **Results from survey on platform requirements (Private):** The document compiles de results from the survey send to i2CAT staff where it is shown a list of requirements prioritised to develop the platform. This dataset will be merged with the surveys in the other locations where data will be aggregated and anonymised.
- **Platform (Private):** It is virtual space where participants can connect with other innovators, share information and resources, collaborate on projects and encourage conversation and the development of opportunities.
- **INTEGER Project | Kick of Meeting | Barcelona, 14 & 15 February 2023 (Private):** Google form to set the logistics for the KOM in Barcelona on 14th and 15th Feb 2023
- **INTEGER Key stakeholders' inputs for the Innovation "4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event (Private):** This is an inquiry in the context of the INTEGER project activities with the goal to collect stakeholders' contribution regarding the need on the field of healthy living in their region.
- **INTEGER project: "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event (Private):** This is the form we used for stakeholders to select their preferred challenge for the event Let's Hack Together!
- **Feedback form INTEGER Model Event Participants WP4_T4.2_Kfeedback from INTEGER Model Event (Private):** This feedback form is directed to participants from "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" during the two moments of virtual interaction together, the 17th and 25th of May and the in-between exchange and co-creation through the INTEGER platform.
- **INTEGER_WP4 Reporting (Private):** This Excel is for WP4 Reporting and it is related to the EU Flagships.

5.2 URV and FURV

- **Contacts of business drivers (Private):** The document compiles the contact details of the business drivers that the URV and the FURV have collected and have contacted them. In addition, the monitoring, and topics of interest for each actor are shown.
- **Datasets related to participation in the capability materials (audiovisual material) (Consortium only):** Audiovisual material produced by business drivers' actors.

5.3 F6S

- **Integer_Building_the Model Event (Private):** Contacts from the actors of the 3 Helix.
- **INTEGER project "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event (respostes) (Consortium only):** Contacts from "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event distributed by groups of work.

5.4 HAM

None identified.

5.5 UJ

- **List of participants of our seminars/workshops (Private):** List with names, family names and institutions, emails.
- **List of participants of the study visits (Private):** List with names, family names and institutions, emails.

5.6 KTP

None identified.

5.7 SHINE

- **Datasets related to project website and social media (tbd):** The project website will establish a web analytics service to gather statistics. Only anonymized data, which cannot be traced back to specific individuals, will be collected. Additionally, social media platforms will utilise their own analytics services to gather and present information regarding user engagement on these platforms.
- **Datasets related to external communication with third parties (tbd):** The project partners will engage and communicate with third parties throughout the project on one or more of the planned activities.
- **Datasets associated with participation in other events, aiming to gather images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination purposes (tbd):** The project will organise activities for which there will be no registration form, and where it may be useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions.

5.8 AFE

- **List of trainees (Private):** People who are trained in different ways are being registered and will receive a badge or certificate/proof.

6 ANNEX I – Informed consent

6.1 Background and aim

INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions is a project under the European Innovation Ecosystems cluster, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme, running from February 2023 to January 2025.

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and wellbeing, INTEGER is bringing forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European Union (EU) innovation ecosystems: the INTEGER 4 Helix Collaboratory model; an EU Healthy Living Collaboratory; a new professional profile, the 'col.laber' or 'col.laboratory manager'.

Based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven and social-driven innovations, INTEGER seeks to accelerate transformative integration outcomes by creating new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, ground-breaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptake and exploitation dynamics.

6.2 Your participation in workshops, other events or interviews/surveys

Your participation in workshops, recordings of image or sound, other events or interviews/surveys is voluntary. You are free to choose which questions you want to answer, and you may leave the workshop or another event at any time without giving any explanation.

6.3 Use of the collected information

We will treat all the information about you with strict confidentiality and in accordance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national data protection laws of the partner that implements the action.

Only the organisation that collects your data, has access to your contact data. When the data collection is completed, all personal data will be anonymised in their further use.

The project partners of INTEGER project will work with the anonymous data afterwards. This will be done according to scientific criteria and with absolutely respect for personal and privacy rights.

Your name and contact information will be deleted before the data is published and no later than January 2025. The rest of the collected data will be securely stored for an indefinite period, as this is a requirement from EC programmes, and for further research purposes.

We will make every effort to ensure that no participant is identifiable in the project report or in any publication based on the workshops; exceptions are only possible if the usage of the name and/or image is desired to be a written declaration.

6.4 Your rights

As long as we can identify your oral and consented visual & sound contributions, you have the right to object to the processing of your personal data, to access, rectify and erase any information about you, and to ask us what information we hold about you. Once details such as your name and address are removed and thus anonymous, then it will no longer be possible to delete the information you provided, as the project partners will not be able anymore to identify its source.

6.5 Responsible organisations

The project partners are: Fundacio Privada I2CAT, Internet I Innovacio Digital A Catalunya (Coordinator); Universitat Rovira I Virgili | Fundació Urv; F6S Innovation; Behoerde Fuer Arbeit, Gesundheit, Soziales, Familie Und Integration Hamburg; Uniwersytet Jagiellonski; Krakow Technology Park; SHINE 2europe; AFEdemy, Academy on Age-Friendly Environments in Europe B. V.

6.6 For more information

<https://integercollab.eu/>

6.7 For more information on the General Data Protection Regulation

https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

6.8 Contacts

[to be added by each partner]

6.9 Declaration of Consent

Please tick all appropriate boxes and return duly signed before the workshop, events, interviews, surveys.

	I hereby declare that I am willing to take part in INTEGER interview.
	I declare that I have been properly informed about the INTEGER project and I understand the written and verbal explanations.
	I was given proper time to reflect on the participation request; I had the opportunity to make the necessary questions and I received satisfactory answers.
	I understand I will be asked if I object that a picture is being taken and I can choose not to appear.
	I authorise that pictures including me can be used in INTEGER's communication and dissemination action, namely in INTEGER social media and website
	I authorise audio records and videos only to be used for analysing the data from the interview/workshop and further technical development, unless stated otherwise
	I authorise audio records and videos also to be used as learning and dissemination materials in the INTEGER social media and website, as from its consortium partners.
	I know that information that I give in an interview or workshop will be analysed and summarised by my interviewer. I will have the right to review its final version, as well as its use for INTEGER outcomes.
	I was informed that the data will only be stored five years after the ending of the project. after which it will be deleted and that I can access or change/delete it at any time.
	I understand that my name, or any information that may identify me personally, will only be displayed with my express consent.
	I understand I can withdraw my participation at any time, without having to give a reason and will have no penalties because of it.
	I would like to receive more information about the INTEGER project and receive the project newsletter to the following email address:

Please, select only one option.

	I allow to share my name, organisation, picture, audio or video record in the integer4h.theglocal.network, social media and website, as well as in different reports and publications within the scope of this project.
	I do not allow my name, organisation, picture, audio or video record to be shared in the integer4h.theglocal.network, social media and website

Participant
Name:
Date and signature:

Researcher informing the participant and
collecting the consent
Name:
Date and signature: